

Table S1. The sh-RNA sequences

Gene	Target position	Sh-RNA sequences
Sh-NC-sense		5'-CACCGTTCTCCGAACGTGTCACGTCAAGAGA TTACGTGACACGTTCCGAGAATTTTTTG-3
Sh-NC-antisense		5'-AGCTCAAAAAATTCTCCGAACGTGTCACGTA ATCTCTGACGTGACACGTTCCGAGAAC-3'
Sh-Linc00668-1-sense		5'-CACCGCTGAAGCAGCATCACTGTCTTTCAAG AGAAGACAGTGATGCTGCTTCAGCTTTTTTG-3'
Sh-Linc00668-1-antisense	180-202	5'-AGCTCAAAAAAGCTGAAGCAGCATCACTGTC TTCTCTTGAAAGACAGTGATGCTGCTTCAGC-3'
Sh-Linc00668-2-sense		5'-CACCGCTTCAAGTTTCATTCTCTCTTTCAAGA GAAGAGAGAATGAACTTGAAGCTTTTTTG-3'
Sh-Linc00668-2-antisense	508-530	5'-AGCTCAAAAAAGCTTCAAGTTTCATTCTCTCT TCTCTTGAAAGAGAGAATGAACTTGAAGC-3'
Sh-Linc00668-3-sense		5'-CACCGTAATCTGGCACGTATAGTTCTTCAAGA GAGAAGACTATACGTGCCAGATTACTTTTTG-3'
Sh-Linc00668-3-antisense	742-764	5'-AGCTCAAAAAAGTAATCTGGCACGTATAGTT CTCTCTTGAAAGAACTATACGTGCCAGATTAC-3'